

Recommended citation: Pinxten, M., Laet, T. D., Soom, C. V., Peeters, C., Kautz, C., Hockicko, P., Pacher, P., Nordström, K., Hawwash, K., & Langie, G. (2017). Approaches to the Identification of STEM Key Competencies in European University Systems . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 389-397). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698114.

Approaches to the Identification of STEM Key Competencies in European University systems

M. PINXTEN

Research Associate Faculty of Engineering Technology
Leuven Engineering and Science Education Center (LESEC), KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium

Maarten.pinxten@kuleuven.be

T. DE LAET

Associate Professor Faculty of Engineering Science
Leuven Engineering and Science Education Center (LESEC), KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium

Tinne.delaet@kuleuven.be

C. VAN SOOM

Associate Professor Faculty of Science
Leuven Engineering and Science Education Center (LESEC), KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium

Carolien.vansoom@kuleuven.be

C. PEETERS

Associate Professor, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering
Leuven Engineering and Science Education Center (LESEC), KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium

Christine.peeters@kuleuven.be

C. KAUTZ

Professor for Engineering Education, Engineering Education Research Group
Hamburg University of Technology
Hamburg, Germany

kautz@tuhh.de

P. HOCKICKO

Associate Professor - Vice-dean for education
Department of Physics, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Žilina
Žilina, Slovakia

hockicko@fyzika.uniza.sk

P. PACHER

Professor, Department of Physics
Department of Physics, Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME)
Budapest, Hungary
pacher@eik.bme.hu

K. NORDSTRÖM

Professor, Program Leader Chemical Engineering
Aalto University
Espoo, Finland
katrina.nordstrom@aalto.fi

K. HAWWASH

Professor, Director of the School of Engineering's Teaching and Learning Centre
Department of Civil Engineering, University of Birmingham
Birmingham, UK
k.i.m.hawwash@bham.ac.uk

G. LANGIE

Professor, Vice Dean Faculty of Engineering Technology
Leuven Engineering and Science Education Center (LESEC) KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium
Greet.langie@kuleuven.be

ABSTRACT

The readySTEMgo project is a collaboration between six European universities: KU Leuven (Belgium), Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH – Germany), University of Žilina (UniZa – Slovakia), Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME – Hungary), University of Birmingham (UK), and Aalto University (Finland). The prime objective of the project is to identify students with an increased drop-out risk before the start or throughout the course of the first-year in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) study programmes.

Before providing an overview of the most salient project findings, we will first address some key issues involved in identifying key entry requirements for first-year science and engineering students in a European framework. A number of institutional (e.g., university entry requirements & secondary school curricula) and diagnostic (e.g., available tests) elements complicate a uniform approach in a diverse European consortium. Against this background, we present the most essential key competences followed by a detailed overview of a number of interventions aimed at at-risk students in the different institutions.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research; Attractiveness of Engineering Education; Skills and Engineering Education

Keywords: Study skills; Achievement; Skills, University entry systems

INTRODUCTION

1 UNIVERSITY ENTRY: INSTITUTIONAL DIVERSITY

1.1 Open admission versus highly selective culture

In general, university entry can best be considered as a continuum between open-admission institutions (i.e., limited entry requirements) and highly selective institutions. We characterize the diversity in university entrance requirements based on three dimensions: (1) Minimal entry criteria; (2) Timing of application, and (3) First-year drop-out rate.

In the readySTEMgo consortium, three universities apply highly selective criteria, namely University of Birmingham (UK), BME (Hungary), and Aalto University (Finland). First, in all three universities, high performance standards based on a nationally organised matriculation exam scores (or the equivalent such as IB and similar) are set as prerequisites for applicants to be eligible to apply. Additionally, at Aalto University applicants' score obtained in a nationally organised entrance exam in math and Physics/Chemistry are considered whereas grades obtained in secondary school are taken into account at BME. Both Aalto University and BME may also admit applicants based on achievements in high-ranking academic competitions, or exceptionally high scores in the matriculation examination [1]. Second, a common feature of all selective institutions is the early application deadline. Applicants need to select the programmes they are applying for in January-March prior to the start of the academic year (BME & Aalto) or even earlier (Birmingham). In the case of Aalto University, secondary school students spend the spring semester working both on matriculation examinations in March and preparing for the entrance examination for university in May. At the University of Birmingham, applicants are even given a full year to work towards the required A-level scores. By the end of the previous academic year, UK students submit their application. Those students of interest to the relevant department are made a conditional offer of a place based on their chosen A-levels. By May of the year of entry students in possession of more than two conditional offers select one university as their firm choice and one, usually requiring a lower set of grades, as insurance. A student who achieves the offer from his firm choice in August of the year of entry has his/her place confirmed. Altogether, secondary school students in highly selective contexts are expected to display higher levels of commitment and goal-orientation in working towards a specific target (see below). Third, drop-out rates are generally substantially lower after the first year in highly selective institutions. For example, at the University of Birmingham less than 5% drops out. Analogously, at BME drop-out ranges between 10-20% over the different engineering programmes.

Medium selective institutions are represented by TUHH (Germany) and UniZa (Slovakia). At UniZa, the final mathematics and physics grades obtained in secondary school and participation in the matriculation exams for these subjects are taken into consideration (since 2008, no STEM subjects are obligatory in the matriculation exam). Applicants who did not participate in the math and/or physics matriculation exam and do not meet the minimal criteria for admittance are obliged to participate in a selection interview on campus. In practice, almost all of these students are accepted because of normative funding [1]. Analogously, at TUHH (Germany) students need to successfully obtain their Abitur matriculation certificate. In theory, admission to TUHH is nominally based on the applicant's results in the matriculation examinations, with a special weight for grades in mathematics. However, due to the legal requirement to not deny admission to anyone as long as the maximum number of students has not been reached (and to the relatively lower interest in engineering careers compared to other fields), admission is not competitive. As a result of normative funding (UniZa) and obligatory admission legislation (TUHH), there is

a high degree of diversity in beginning students' prior exposure to instruction and in their skills in science and mathematics. The decision-making and application process takes place at a later stage compared to highly selective institutions (after the matriculation exams) and drop-out rates are higher. For example, for some programmes at UniZa, drop-out rates after the first year can get as high as 50%.

KU Leuven (Belgium) is a university at the open-admission end of the spectrum. In Belgium, only minimal requirements apply for entering a science or engineering bachelor. Any student with a diploma of secondary education is allowed to enrol in any programme they want (except for medicine), regardless of their prior achievements or educational background. The secondary school diploma is not obtained on the basis of a nationally organised matriculation exam but exam grades at the end of secondary school. As a result, a large number of students subscribe for a science or engineering programme only one or two months before the start of the academic year at KU Leuven. For example, in 2015-2016, 30% of the students made their final decision during the summer holiday prior to the academic year. The proportion of students who drop out after the first year lies around 30%, a number that is fairly stable over the last years.

1.2 Consequence of different admission criteria

The aforementioned institutional diversity in terms of entry requirements has important consequences for the realisation of the objectives of the readySTEMgo project. A uniform approach focusing on STEM course content is highly impractical because of the heterogeneity in first-year student populations: highly selective universities select a population of high-achieving students whereas at more open-admission universities there is a wider range of achievement levels of incoming students. A single scientific measurement in full alignment with the different secondary school STEM curricula at the partner countries is not feasible.

Therefore, we did not focus on cognitive key skills such as prior knowledge in the fields of mathematics, physics, biology and chemistry. There is ample evidence for the importance of prior achievement levels in these fields for student achievement in higher education [2]. Instead, it was decided to shift the focus to more non-cognitive skills that (1) have the potential to be a predictor of study success, (2) offer concrete targets for improvement, and (3) can be measured through existing validated instruments. In the following two paragraphs we give an overview of our results.

2 KEY COMPETENCES: DUAL APPROACH

All partners agreed that, irrespective of the context, first-year students are confronted with large amounts of challenging course material. Students are expected to be architects of their own learning process and to make use of the resources available to them to master the required knowledge levels. As such, we decided to focus on (1) incoming student's learning/study strategies and attitudes towards learning (KU Leuven, TUHH, UniZa, BME, and University of Birmingham) and (2) levels of conceptual understanding in the field of mechanics, a central topic in most engineering programmes (TUHH and UniZa). At Aalto University, we mainly focused on the evaluation of interventions which are aimed to support integration of freshmen into student and academic communities.

2.1 Learning and study strategies

At the start of the academic years 2015-2016 and 2016-2017, the Learning And Study Strategies Inventory (LASSI, [3]) was presented to 7168 first-year students at KU Leuven,

UniZa, BME, and the University of Birmingham. Except for the latter university, we were able to link these test results to student's obtained grades after the first semester at university. Our results show that students' self-regulatory skills levels (e.g., time management, concentration when studying, and motivation/persistence) were all significantly related to student achievement. Fig. 1 presents the results for the time management scale. In all three universities there was a positive relationship between better time management skills and student achievement (expressed as the proportion of ECTS credits obtained) in the exams in January: students with poor time management skills obtain significantly less credits compared to students with better time management skills. Similar patterns were observed for the other self-regulatory scales.

Fig. 1. Relationship between time management skills at the start and student achievement after the first examinations at university in 2016-2017 (KU Leuven, UniZa, and BME).

In sum, engineering students' self-regulatory skills levels at the start of university have important consequences for their achievement later on. Measuring the levels of self-regulating skills of incoming students may enable identification of students with an increased propensity to underperform or to drop out of the programme. Although this relation is supported in both open-admission (KU Leuven) and highly selective institutions (BME), this particularly applies for students from universities with a semi selective or open-admission culture since most of these students have not previously been required to attain externally set high level standards. In contrast, challenging target scores set by highly selective institutions require high degrees of self-regulation in the last stage of secondary school towards the matriculation exams. In order to illustrate this claim, the self-reported effort levels of students in secondary school in Belgium (KU Leuven) and the UK (Birmingham) are compared (Fig. 2). More specifically, during the first week of the academic year, students were requested to rate the following item on a 5-point Likert type scale: "I had to work hard for my obtained study results in secondary education". 61% of the first-year students at the University of Birmingham agreed with this statement whereas for KU Leuven, this is only 13%.

Fig. 2. Comparison of effort levels in secondary school in a highly selective (University of Birmingham) and an open-admission (KU Leuven) context.

2.2 Conceptual understanding

At TUHH and UniZa, a strong focus is on the conceptual understanding of students in the field of mechanics. It can be argued that students with a limited conceptual understanding at the start of an introductory Physics/Mechanics course are also at-risk. Both at UniZa and TUHH, rigorous pre and post test procedures (using the Force Concept Inventory and/or similar diagnostic tests), enable the determination of learning gains in terms of increased conceptual understanding after an introductory Physics/Mechanics course. Additionally, TUHH researchers examined the epistemological beliefs of first-year students about doing physics. For example, before the start of a large introductory mechanics course, 80% of the students indicated that they need to make sense out of formulas before they could use them correctly, and that they think it is useful to spent time on understanding where formulas are coming from.

In terms of learning gains in conceptual understanding, it was shown that interactive video teaching methods produced significantly higher learning gains compared to more traditional teaching methods.

3 INTERVENTIONS: A MULTIFACETED APPROACH

3.1 KU Leuven: Interactive student dashboard

At the start of the academic year 2016-2017, 1509 first-year students in the STEM field filled in the LASSI questionnaire regarding their learning and study behaviour in secondary school. Rather than only using the collected data for research purposes in the readySTEMgo project, it was decided to provide students with individual feedback on their personal scores on each scale. With the help of the researchers of the STELA project (www.stela-project.eu), an interactive feedback dashboard was developed with a central focus on actionable feedback (i.e., feedback that provides students with very concrete targets for improvement, [4]). The prime objective of this dashboard is to unveil information to first-year students on their personal self-regulatory skills (i.e., Concentration, Time management, Motivation/persistence, Anxiety, and Test strategies) and to stimulate a self-reflective process on their own learning behaviour. In order to avoid complex statistical interpretations, the dashboard uses simple visualizations complemented with textual explanations and concrete tips for improvement. 1406 students with a complete profile received an invitation by mail to consult their individual scores in the middle of the first

semester. Altogether, 1135 (80.7%) of the students clicked on the link in the invitation email and entered the dashboard. 81.2% of the students that did click through, did so within three days. The proportions of students who consulted the improvement tips ranged between 15.2% (Performance anxiety) and 35.2% (Concentration). Additionally, the researchers found that students with a lower score on the five scales display higher levels of interaction with the platform (e.g., going back to an earlier page/tab, click on the improvement tips,...). For example, students with higher levels of performance anxiety consulted the improvement tips significantly more frequently compared to less anxious students.

3.2 UniZa: Physics summer course

In the framework of the readySTEMgo project, a summer course in physics was organised for the first time at Uniza. In this first edition, 87 students participated. In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the summer course, three evaluation criteria were put forward: (1) increased conceptual understanding of basic Newtonian Physics; (2) self-perceived usefulness in the short run; and (3) self-perceived usefulness in the long run (i.e., after the first semester). Of the 87 participants, 36 students participated in both the FCI pre and posttest. Statistical differences between the pre ($M=27.41$, $SD=10.69$) and posttest ($M=42.04$, $SD=12.27$) scores were tested using a t-test. The results clearly show a significantly higher post-test score after participating in the summer course $t(35)=9.76$, $p<0.001$. These results suggest that the summer course contributes to students' understanding of Newtonian physics. Second, in general, students reported high satisfaction levels with the summer course. On a 5-point Likert type scale, participating students consider the summer course to be very important ($M = 4.4$, $SD=0.81$) and useful ($M = 4.5$, $SD=0.55$). Even after the first semester Physics course, 78% of the respondents considered the summer course to be (very) useful and 69% of the respondents indicated that they were better able to check their prior physics knowledge.

3.3 TUHH: Tutorials & interactive teaching methods

Tutorials are defined as collaborative group activities that focus on instructional materials to target common misconceptions. In these tutorial sessions, a qualitative approach to problem solving is stimulated by trained assistants who guide a group of 20-25 students through the learning process by asking a number of specific questions. Evaluation of Tutorial instruction had begun prior to the start of the readySTEMgo project by collecting data on the level of expertise in the field of mechanics among incoming students. Through subsequent testing at the end of a first-semester Statics course, the effect of instruction with and without the use of Tutorials (for equal amounts of contact time) could be measured and compared. As the diagram of post-test versus pre-test scores from multiple years of instruction indicates, there is a statistically significant and practically relevant improvement of post-test scores for students of all levels of prior knowledge.

3.4 Aalto University: ABC-introduction week and student guilds

Prior to the start of the academic year, students at Aalto University are obliged to take part in a one-week intensive introduction course, which is later followed up by other supporting courses, such as the Academic Learning Community studies. Rather than focusing on the transfer of academic course content, the prime objective of this introduction week is to coach incoming students to adopt valuable learning and study strategies. Additionally, students are introduced to the student guilds and to their mentors at university. In the readySTEMgo project, we evaluated the self-perceived usefulness of the introduction week after two semesters at university. 46 out of 146 first-year students at the CHEM school filled in an online survey regarding the ABC introduction week and the student guilds.

Fig. 3. Comparison of conceptual learning gains between interactive teaching methods (with tutorials) and traditional teaching methods at TUHH.

Altogether, 46% of the respondents agreed that the ABC-introduction week helped to them plan their studies. Only 13% of the students indicated that the ABC-introduction week has helped them to identify their strengths and weaknesses as a student. Peer support by the student guild showed to be an important resource for first-year students: 67% of the respondents indicated that the student guilds helped them to deal with school related pressure. Overall, it is evident that the peer support through social activities arranged by the guild, the mentoring system run by the guild and the extension into non-academic issues in student lives, identifies the student guild as a key element for student well-being. This has a clear positive effect on student attitudes towards tackling academic challenges.

3.5 BME: Math diagnostic test and bridging courses after enrolment

Since 2010, an obligatory math diagnostic test (*'math zero test'*) at the start of the first semester (after enrolment), was introduced at BME. The need for the diagnostic test as part of the course requirements in first semester mathematics was generated by the current inconsistencies of the admission system of the Hungarian higher education, namely the weak correlation between admission points and diagnostic test scores [5].

Despite the high entrance score, many first-year students fail the math zero test. In the academic year 2016-2017, results of the readySTEMgo project showed that 23% of the students who failed the math zero test (N=380) obtained less than 50% of their credits after the exams in January 2017. For students who passed the math zero test (N=358), this number decreased to 8%. These results show that, even after a rigorous selection process, an obligatory math diagnostic test has added value in identifying at-risk students.

In order to support at-risk students in the transition to higher education, bridging courses in mathematics were introduced at all faculties. At the Faculty of Chemical Technology and Biotechnology, mandatory bridging courses in physics and chemistry (2 ECTS credits) were organised in addition to the bridging math course. Before the introduction of the bridging math course, more than 30% of the first-year students failed the "Mathematics 1" course. As a result of the participation in the bridging math course, the number of students who did not pass dropped drastically (below 20%). The effectiveness of both the bridging chemistry and physics course is similar: the failure rate dropped from about 50% to 25%.

4 SUMMARY

An important challenge for an international research consortium is the strict privacy legislation in some universities. In some cases, researchers are unable to gather data where student identity numbers would be matched with students grades through the official records (for example, Aalto University, University of Birmingham & TUHH). At the latter university, researchers administered an experimental approach with self-generated ID's in order to ask students directly for their self-reported grades (rather than access these data directly from the university records). Aalto University requires that use of data must be specified for a particular purpose, written consent is required, and data must be in a format that cannot be traced back to the individual. This is a challenge for studies which aim to follow progress of an individual student. Moreover, Aalto University collects an abundance of information at regular intervals for internal and external use. An attempt was made to collect data at Aalto for the present study, but the response of students in a highly complicated privacy setting in the present study, produced a very low response rate. As a consequence of these privacy regulations, we were not able to link the measured skills with students' actual performance in each university.

The common goal for all the partner universities is to deliver the best scientist and engineers by providing a study environment that (1) optimally supports the development of STEM skills and (2) engages into learning outcomes that lead to high employment of future graduates. On the other hand, even in the post-Bologna era, the readySTEMgo project has revealed that there are very divergent models and approaches for achieving learning outcomes in universities with very different institutional contexts. Each institution deals with its own challenges in a number of ways, ranging from a well-organised mentoring and guild system, an individual feedback system on learning strategies, interactive teaching methods, or STEM bridging courses. A thorough understanding of this diversity provided a number of interesting learning opportunities for all participating partners and helped to understand why successful educational recipes of one educational context cannot be univocally transferred to another.

REFERENCES

- [1] Pinxten M., Van Soom C., Peeters C., De Laet T., Pacher P., Hockicko P. and Langie G. (2016). Learning and study strategies of incoming science and engineering students. A comparative study between three institutions in Belgium, Slovakia, and Hungary. *Proceedings of the 44rd Annual SEFI Conference*. Annual SEFI Conference. Tampere, Finland, 12-15 September 2016.
- [2] Pinxten M., De Laet T., Van Soom C., Langie G. (2015). Fighting increasing drop-out rates in the STEM field: The European readySTEMgo Project. *Proceedings of the 43rd Annual SEFI Conference*. Annual Conference of European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI). Orléans, France, 1-3 July 2015
- [3] Weinstein, C.E., & Palmer D.R. (2002). *Learning and Study Strategies Inventory 2nd Edition*. Clearwater, FL: H&H Publishing Company.
- [4] Broos, T., Peeters, L., Verbert, K., Van Soom, C., Langie, G., De Laet, T. (2017). Dashboard for Actionable Feedback on Learning Skills: Scalability and Usefulness. *Proceedings of the 19th Human Computer Interaction (HCI) Conference*. Vancouver (Canada), 9-14 July 2017.
- [5] Csákány, A. (2012). Assessment of first year engineering students in mathematics at Budapest University of Technology and Economics, *Proceedings of the 16th SEFI MWG Seminar*, Salamanca, Spain, 28-30 June 2012